

Adsorption by Polar Precipitate. Part III. Electro-osmotic Experiments with Silver Iodide.

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In a recent paper on the adsorption of ions by freshly prepared lead chromate, it has been pointed out (Mukherjee and Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173) that electro-osmotic experiments give us a better idea of the adsorption of ions than analytical methods. They point out that the latter do not give any indication as to whether the adsorbed ions replace those of the same sign in the crystal lattice thus leaving the crystal and its surface electrically neutral, or are adsorbed on the surface (without exchange of ions) which consequently becomes electrically charged through an excess of the adsorption of ions of one sign. Electro-osmotic measurements enable us to follow the relative adsorption of ions of both sign. It has also been pointed out that analytical methods give an idea of the net exchange of ions between the double layer and the solution, but our observations on the variation of the charge on the surface give us an idea of the adsorption of ions of both sign in the fixed layer of ions on the surface (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 1, 213). Taylor and Beekley (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 22, 912) have recently measured by analytical methods the adsorption of ions by precipitated silver iodide. They point out the desirability of studying the adsorption of substances by chemically pure substances

and they worked with silver iodide as it can be prepared in a very pure condition.

In the present paper the results of experiments with silver iodide similar to those already carried out with lead chromate are recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The arrangement we used for electro-osmotic measurements is a modified form of that used by Briggs (Mukherjee and Roy, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, *I*, 173). The results are reproducible within ± 7 per cent. The precipitate was shaken with water or electrolyte in a stopper Jena glass bottle, kept for 24 hours and then poured in the U-tube. The precipitate being heavy settled within an hour.

The preparation and purification of the precipitate require great care and in this matter, the procedure described by Taylor and Beekley (*loc. cit.*) has been scrupulously followed. The silver iodide thus obtained was found to be free from adsorbed and occluded salts and to be quite insensitive to light as stated by the above authors.

The results are given in Tables I and II. The figures give the movement of the bubble in cm. per minute. The sign indicates the sign of the charge carried by the particles. The concentrations are given in gram equivalents per litre. At concentrations higher than those in the table, the results become unreliable on account of electrolysis.

TABLE I.¹

Electrolytic concentration.	AgNO ₃	KCl	K ₂ SO ₄	KBr	KI
0	-6.6	-6.6	-6.6	-6.6	-6.6
.0001	+7.3	-11.4	...		
.0002	+8.1	-12.9	-15.3		-12.5
.0004	+10.5	-15.3	...		-12.7
.001	12.5	-6.7	-18.2	-21.7	-15.0
.002	electrolysis	-18.2	-19.4	-20.8(?)	electrolysis
.004	...	-20.2	-18.7	-23.0	

TABLE II.

Electrolytic concentration.	KI	KNO ₃	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	Al(NO ₃) ₃
0	-3.9	-3.9	-3.9	-3.9	-3.9
.0002	-9.9	-13.1	-6.2		
.001	-13.8	-16.8	-8.5	-8.7	-4.5
.002		-18.4	-9.8	-9.9	-4.5
.004		-19.1	-9.6	-10.0	-3.5

DISCUSSION.

A. Change in Contact with Water.

We find that, similar to what has been observed in the case of lead chromate, purified silver iodide is negatively charged in contact with water. In view of the case taken to prepare the substance free from

¹ A different sample of silver iodide was used in this experiment.

electrolytes and the fact that silver nitrate was present in excess at the time of precipitation, one may assume that the negative charge is not due to an adsorption of an excess of iodine ions by the surface. If this be true, then the initial negative charge may be ascribed to either of two sources :

(1) A preferential adsorption of hydroxyl ions from water, or (2) what appears more probable on theoretical grounds, silver ions are perhaps held less strongly on the surface than iodine ions. It is possible to imagine that some of the silver ions on the surface, in virtue of their thermal energy, loosen themselves from the lattice and form the mobile sheet of the double layer.

From the point of view of the latter alternative all that we need assume is that at any instant under consideration a number of silver ions remain near the surface in a mobile state and take part in the conduction of electricity when a potential gradient acts along the surface. The assumption that the iodine ion is more intensely held in the lattice than the silver ion is in keeping with the well-known fact that the transference of electricity in solid silver iodide and many other salts takes place mainly through the positive ion. However we shall see presently that iodine ions are apparently less strongly adsorbed than silver ions and that further work is necessary before we can be sure as to the validity of this explanation.

B. Adsorption of Constituent Ions.

Unlike the case of lead chromate we find that, of the constituent ions though silver ions are adsorbed much more strongly than the other cations we have used, iodine ions are adsorbed less strongly than most of the other univalent anions. The intensity of adsorption of silver

ions is apparent from the fact that at a concentration of 0.001 normal, the rate of electro-osmotic flow has changed from 6.6 to 12.5, whereas at the same concentration, the adsorption of iodine ions has increased the rate of flow from 6.6 to 15.0. The weakness of the adsorption of iodine ions is unexpected and difficult to account. Even assuming that the initial negative charge is to be ascribed to the excess of iodine ions on the surface over silver ions, the magnitude of the change in the positive charge points to a stronger adsorption of silver ions. Further the nitrate ion is more strongly adsorbed than other anions and taking this into consideration, we find that adsorption of silver ions is greater than that indicated by the rate of electro-osmotic flow. It is also not possible to refer the weak effect of iodine ions to strong adsorption of potassium ions, as it is well known that alkali metal ions are not primarily adsorbed (*cf.* Mukherjee and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 476) while the electro-osmotic data point to weak adsorption of iodine ions, we are prevented from drawing a definite conclusion, as we have also observed that in the presence of potassium iodide the precipitate breaks up into smaller particles. Until the increased frictional resistance that is to be expected from a diminution in the size of the particles has been taken into account, the question must be left open.¹

C. Adsorption of other Ions.

As usual we notice the valency effects of cations on the negatively charged surface. So far as we could observe visually we found that the other electrolytes do

¹ Hitherto all methods which have been used for measuring the rate of electro-osmotic flow overlook this source of error. An apparatus, obviating this and other sources of error in the measurements, has been devised in this laboratory but it has not yet reached a convenient form.

not produce a change in the size of the particles of the precipitate. Comparing the different potassium salts other than the iodide we observe that bromide increases the negative charge to the greatest extent.

Taking into account the differences in the negative charge of the two samples of silver iodide it appears that the nitrate ion is more adsorbed than the chloride ion. Considering also that the adsorption of a sulphate ion means an increase of two units of negative charge, the adsorption of sulphate ion is weakest of the anions we have used. The order of adsorption of anions therefore appears to be bromide > nitrate > chloride > sulphate. Excepting the nitrate, the order is the same as that of increasing solubility. As with lead chromate we notice that the nitrate is more adsorbable and that the solubility of the nitrate gives us no idea as to the adsorbability of the nitrate ion. We observe that, barring the iodide, these results are very similar to what has been observed with lead chromate. The solubility of the corresponding salt appears to be one of the factors determining the intensity of adsorption, though it is evident that other factors have also to be considered. Lastly we would point out that electro-osmotic experiments give us an idea of the relative adsorption of the cation and anion on the surface, whereas analytical measurements of adsorption give us an idea of the adsorption as a whole in the double layer.

Summary and Conclusion.

(a) Purified silver iodide carries a negative charge in contact with water.

(b) Of the cations—silver, potassium, calcium, barium, aluminium—silver reverses the charge on the surface and imparts a strong positive charge to it and the order of adsorption is $\text{Ag} > \text{Al} > \text{Ba} : \text{Ca} > \text{K}$.

(c) As opposed to the well known strong adsorption of constituent ions we have observed that the iodine ion is very weakly adsorbed by silver iodide. This is surprising in view of the observations of Lottermoser and of Fajans and Beekerath (*Z. Physikal Chem.*, 1921, 97, 478) that constituent ions are strongly adsorbed by insoluble silver salts. It has been pointed out, however, that diminution of the size of the particles takes place when the precipitate is in contact with potassium iodide and the increased frictional resistance may explain our observation.

(d) Of the other anions the order of adsorption appears to be $\text{Br}' > \text{NO}_3' > \text{Cl}' > \text{SO}_4''$.

(e) Attention has been drawn to the necessity of simultaneous measurement of frictional resistance of the diaphragm in electro-osmotic experiments—a source of error not taken into consideration in the methods of measurement which are in use.